

Thermosensitivity of rice seeds grown by farmers

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Treating rice seeds with hot water is recommended to control externally and internally borne pathogens like fungi, bacteria, and nematodes. Treatment use is limited because of the differential sensitivity of seeds to hot water. It is necessary to determine the thermosensitivity of seed of different rice varieties before subjecting them to hot water treatment. This study was made to ascertain rice sensitivity to hot water treatment at recommended temperatures (52 or 54°C).

Seeds of 13 improved semidwarf rice varieties — IR8 (Peta/DgWg), Vani (IR8/CR1014), Jagannath (TI41 mutant), Kalinga-1 (Dungharsali/IR8), Ratna (TKM6/IR8), Pankaj (Tonkai Raton/Peta), Parijat (TKM6/TN1), Indira (Tainan 3 mutant), CR 158-5008-52-212, CR10-4181-10, CR9242, local Athgadi, BJ 1 — and the improved tall variety TI41 were collected from farmers in the CRRI Operational Research Project Area at Kandarpur in Cuttack, Orissa.

Twenty-five grams seed of each variety were placed in separate cloth bags, soaked in room temperature water for 8 hours, and then separately treated in a Kilburn hot water bath at 52 or 54°C for 10, 20, and 30 minutes. They were then dipped in water at room temperature. Untreated controls were main-

Percentage of seed germination of rice varieties treated with hot water at 52 and 54°C for 10, 20, and 30 minutes in Cuttack, India.

Variety	Temperature (°C)	Germination (%)			
		Control	10 min	20 min	30 min
IR8	52	59.00	46.50	34.50	21.75
	54	59.25	40.50	26.25	18.00
Vani	52	29.00	29.75	25.50	26.75
	54	41.00	40.00	35.00	25.50
Jagannath	52	51.25	40.00	23.60	14.00
	54	54.00	35.00	21.50	8.50
CR9242	52	45.25	35.00	24.25	20.50
	54	48.00	40.00	28.75	23.25
Kalinga-1	52	58.50	60.00	45.75	35.00
	54	61.75	59.00	44.50	32.25
CR158-5008-52-212	52	53.75	38.75	29.75	29.25
	54	49.50	38.50	29.00	24.00
TI41	52	57.50	60.00	40.00	41.50
	54	60.50	58.25	38.50	30.75
Ratna	52	74.50	71.00	68.50	68.75
	54	77.25	77.50	69.00	42.25
Athgadi	52	69.25	66.25	58.00	39.00
	54	70.00	67.00	53.00	29.75
Pankaj	52	72.50	69.25	55.00	57.75
	54	71.75	66.00	48.50	26.50
BJ 1	52	50.00	52.50	48.00	45.00
	54	55.75	54.00	46.50	41.00
CR10-4181-10	52	46.00	44.00	47.00	44.75
	54	48.15	44.50	32.25	27.00
Indira	52	79.00	74.00	76.25	77.25
	54	81.50	74.00	45.75	35.00
Parijat	52	66.75	54.00	42.25	31.00
	54	72.50	58.25	44.00	33.50

tained for each variety and treatment. Germination of 400 seeds was tested by the blotter method.

Germination was reduced for all varieties when seeds were placed in 54°C water for 30 minutes. Seeds of Ratna, Indira, BJ 1, CR10-4181-10, and Vani were insensitive to treatment at 52°C for 30 minutes. Athgadi, Kalinga-1, TI41,

and Pankaj were insensitive to 52 and 54° C temperatures when exposed for 10 minutes only, but germination was reduced when the seeds were exposed for 20 or 30 minutes. Jagannath, IR8, CR9242, CR158-5008-52-212, and Parijat were very sensitive to hot water. Germination declined as exposure time and temperature increased (see table).

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

Yield, plant characteristics, and quality of some rice varieties in the Amazon Valley

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Five to ten million hectares in the lower Amazon basin of Brazil are swampy for most of the year. Little land is reclaimed

for planting. At São Raimundo, land was diked and a fully mechanized project established. Seeding and fertilizer and pesticide application are done aerially. Crops are harvested by combines. Electric pumps facilitate irrigation and drainage.

Soils are acidic and have high exchangeable iron and aluminum content. In a preliminary seed multiplication

trial superior varieties were selected. Using these varieties, a replicated yield trial was conducted in 1981 to isolate high yielding varieties with good grain quality. Rough rice yields at 14% moisture and plant ancillary characteristics are in Table 1. Milling yields and grain quality are in Table 2.

Varieties had significant yield differences. Variety J-229 is the present com-